

Technical Report Of

ROHU BREEDING

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Rohu breeding.

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1. Introduction of Rohu carp.

- ❖ Habitat- rivers and lakes
- ❖ Feeding – The species is an omnivore with specific food preferences at different life stages. During the early stages of its lifecycle, it eats mainly zooplankton, but as it grows, it eats more and more phytoplankton, and as a juvenile or adult is a herbivorous column feeder, eating mainly phytoplankton and submerged vegetation.
- ❖ Fecundity 100000/kg
- ❖ Maturity:- 2-3 Years
- ❖ Maximum growth-20kg

2. Selecting of brooders.

Selecting the right brooders is crucial for successful rohu breeding. Here are some key factors to consider:

- ❖ Age and size - Select sexually mature brooders, typically 3-5 years old and weighing 2-5 kg. Younger or older fish may not produce optimal quality eggs or sperm.
- ❖ Body shape and condition - Choose brooders with health, free from injuries or deformities. The abdomen of females should be rounded, while males should have a slim body shape
- ❖ Fins and scales - Fins should be free of damage. Scales should be smooth and shiny will indicate good health.
- ❖ Disease-free - Choose brooders free from any visible signs of diseases or parasites. It is important to maintain good water quality and hygiene practices during the rearing period to prevent infections.
- ❖ History of breeders - It is important to select brooders with a history of successful spawning and good egg quality.
- ❖ Stress levels - Avoid stressed brooders as it can negatively impact sperm and egg quality.

- ❖ Avoid inbreeding - Select brooders from different genetic backgrounds to minimize the risk of deformation

It is important to maintain optimal water quality parameters like temperature, dissolved oxygen, and ph. And provide nutritious feed to ensure optimal brood stock health and egg quality.

3. Conditioning

- ❖ After selecting proper brood stock they are transferred to net house unit for conditioning.
- ❖ Proper conditioning of Rohu brood stock is crucial for successful spawning and offspring production.
- ❖ It helps to minimize stress factors like handling, loud noises, or sudden changes in water parameters. It creates a calm and conducive environment for brood stock.
- ❖ They provide temporary net cage for brood-stock for conditioning. And maintain good aeration conditions, ideal water temperature (26-29 0C) and pH level (6.5 -7.5)
- ❖ They keep brooders for about 5 hours in the conditioning unit

4. Hormone injection.

Oviulin hormone is used for this purpose. 0.5 ml - 1kg is used for female fish. During the injection, the injection is made into the pectoral fin muscle. The fish are weighed before injection to determine the amount of hormone they should receive.

5. After conditioning.

After injecting the hormones, they are transferred to the spawning tank.

6. Preparation of spawning tank

Set up a large tank (around 1000 liters) with good water flow, aeration, and spawning substrate (e.g., hapa nets, aquatic plants). Here the fish are created in natural conditions. Maintain the water temperature at 26-28°C.

7. Spawning and laying eggs.

Between 8-10 pm, females lay eggs and males ovulate.

8. Removal of brood stock after laying eggs.

After laying the eggs, the brood stock fishes should be removed from the spawning tank. The mother animals should be removed so as not to damage the eggs.

9. Collecting the eggs and transferring them to the Hatchery Jar.

Here, the eggs are collected by the harpa net placed on the bottom of the tank. Rohu eggs are then transferred to the Hatchery Jar to provide the necessary conditions for embryo development in the eggs. The Hatchery jar provides oxygen to the eggs and fertilization takes place in the eggs for quick development of the embryo.

10. Egg counting.

Here eggs are taken in a 100ml beaker and the amount of eggs in it is measured and compared with the number of eggs that can be put in the Hatchery jar completely and the amount of eggs is determined.

11. Observation of Rohu carp eggs by using microscope. (Embryonic cleavage)

The development of the embryo inside the egg was observed with the help of a microscope. Every two hours, embryos were observed to divide and grow inside the eggs.

Stage 01

Stage 02

Stage 03

Stage 04

Stage 05

Stage 06

Stage 07

12. Hatching eggs.

It takes almost 12 hours for the chicks to hatch from the eggs. It is called PL (Primary Larvae).

Stage 08

13. Feeding the primary larvae.

Here the feeding of small fish is done after a day. They are given egg solution as food. It is sufficient to use two or three eggs for the egg solution.

Egg mixture preparation

14. Mud pond preparation.

Cleaning and preparation of a mud pond.

The pond is the habitat of cultivated fish. Cleaning and disinfection of ponds is the basis for establishing a good environment for fish. Pond clearance is one of the most critical techniques for disease prevention success and high production.

Before cleaning and preparing a mud pond, drain the water completely through the outlet, then remove excess silt, unwanted debris and moss from the bottom of the pond and expose the pond bottom to sunlight (sun drying) Keep the bottom soil moist after drying. Otherwise, the micro biota will not be active and the organic matter will fail to decompose and the pond will not be fertilized. Sludge ponds are usually de-silted and disinfected once a year.

After removing excess silt, moss and unwanted debris, they use bleaching powder (30-40 grams per 1 m) to disinfect mud ponds, which kills pathogens and wild fish, regulates water quality and fertility. Or we can use CaCO_3 (100-200g for 1m²) to disinfect mud ponds. After that, they let the pond dry for a day. The next day, new water is filled to a height of 2 meters. A net is applied to the inlet pipe to control the entry of wild fish / fish eggs / insects / insect larvae / snails / weeds. Kerosene is applied 2-3 hours before (1400 ft² - 01 L) after filling with new water. After that a new fry is introduced.

Steps of Pond Preparation

❖ **Cleaning**

- Clean around the pool
- Clean the side layer
- Repairing pond disk
- Remove bivalves
- Remove microphytes.

❖ **Eradication**

Chemical methods

- Bleaching
- Lime

Physical methods

- * Sunlight

❖ **Watering**

❖ **Fertilization**

Put cow dung for fertilize ponds

❖ **Inoculation**

Zooplankton which are already grown in a tank is added to fertilize tank

❖ **Controlling insects**

Add kerosene oil – this shouldn't be added when it may be rained or hard sun shining.

Cleaning the mud pond

Eradication (Bleaching)

15. Introduce of primary larvae fish into mud ponds.

The fry are kept in the Hatchery Jar for almost two to three days. Once they start swimming and their limbs are fully developed, they start to change from white to black and their eyes start to become fully visible. Then they are transplanted into mud ponds.

16. Feeding after introduced in to the mud ponds.

We can feed soya milk for the rohu primary larvae after the introduced to the mud ponds.

Soya milk as fish food

Soy milk can be used as fish feed and is a valuable source of protein and nutrients for larval fish such as carp and tilapia, but its suitability and effectiveness depends on several factors.

01. Fish Species

Different species of fish have different nutritional requirements. Some fish, such as carp and tilapia, can thrive on soy milk as a significant part of their diet. Soy milk is used as a starter food, especially during the primary larval stage

02. Age and Stage of Development

Young fish such as fry and fry have different nutritional needs than adults. Soy milk can be a good source of protein and nutrients for young fish, but it may need to be supplemented with other ingredients.

03. Cost and Availability

Soy milk can be a cost-effective alternative to traditional fish feed, especially in areas where fish feed is expensive or scarce. However, the price and availability of soy milk can also vary by location.

Benefits of using soya milk as larval fish feed

- ❖ Soya milk can improve the growth and survival of larval fish.
- ❖ It can improve the nutritional quality of fish meat.
- ❖ Soy milk is a relatively inexpensive food source.
- ❖ Soy milk can be used to fertilize ponds and increase the growth of natural food organisms for fish.

Challenges of using soya milk as larval fish feed

- ❖ Soya milk may be difficult for some larval fish to digest.
- ❖ It can cause water quality problems if not used properly.
- ❖ Soy milk may contain anti-nutritional factors that may reduce its nutritional value.

Overall, soya milk can be a valuable and sustainable source of protein and nutrients for fish feed, but it is important to consider the specific needs of the fish species, the processing methods used and possible deficiencies.

Soya milk making procedure;

1. Sun drying soybeans

The drying process removes moisture from the beans, which prevents the growth of mold and bacteria, and it removes other insects and debris from the soybean seeds.

Also, various fungal and bacterial infections are reduced and the seeds are slightly sterilized.

Therefore, sun drying is a natural way to preserve soybeans. This extends the shelf life of soybeans and reduces the risk of spoilage.

Sun drying soy beans

2. Soaking

Soaking soybeans is a crucial step in making soy milk. It helps extract nutrients and flavors from the beans, resulting in smooth and creamy milk.

After drying, soybeans are soaked in water for about 12 hours to make them easier to grind. Usually they soak about 5 kg of soybeans at a time.

3. Grinding

Here the soaked soybeans are mixed with water and ground as soy milk. They have an electric grinder for making soy milk.

Soy grinding machine

Here, milled soy flakes and powder are removed as a by-product and are sometimes fed to chicken farmers as poultry feed.

Usually 5 kg of soaked soya produces 02 buckets of soya milk (8-10 liters of soya milk).

A by-product of the soy milk grinder

4. Feeding

They feed soy milk to the larvae by mixing/mixing it directly into the rearing water. The amount of soy milk used must be carefully controlled to avoid water quality problems due to excess nutrients.

They feed the larvae several times a day, but in small amounts to prevent water quality problems and monitor the larvae for signs of stress or poor growth. Then adjust feeding frequency, concentration or method as needed.

Regularly monitor water quality parameters such as pH, ammonia and nitrite levels. Excess nutrients from soy milk can affect these parameters, so we must be prepared to adjust water changes or aeration accordingly.

Usually they apply 4-5 liters of soy milk 03 times a day per larval mud pond.

Soy milk

feeding soy milk